

A Theological Examination of the Concept of Sin: Hamartiology and the Good News

“**F**or the LORD is just, he loves just deeds, the upright shall see his face” (Psalms 11:7)

['STRENGTH FROM SCARS' - Robert Charles Kavanagh](#)

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From a contemporary perspective, humanity falls exceedingly short of what might be described as its “universal code of conduct.”^[1] Humankind knows this because they have a conscience that allows them to know better.^[2] Atheists often argue that Darwinism demonstrates that humans have progressed to a milder, tolerant, and submissive temperament over time.^[3] But despite this argument, success in this world is often characterised by lying, cheating, brutality, violence, and even genocide. This demonstrates that, at least from a scientific point of view,^[4] humanity’s significant infringement of its “universal code of conduct”^[5] is at odds with Darwin’s idea. Only God can explain this conundrum through the Doctrine of Sin. The whole concept of sin is imputed to, or inherited by, humanity (known as Original Sin), and no matter how good humans set out to be, evil (the serpent) is always lurking, and personal sin can be committed. As the apostle Paul says (in Romans 7:21–23):

When I want to do good, evil is right there with me. For in my inner being I delight in God’s law; but I see ... law at work in the members of my body, waging war against the law of my mind and making me prisoner of the law of sin at work within my members.

The terrible reality of sin is that it disconnects humankind from God (Romans 3:21; Hebrews 6:6), and they will be punished (albeit “lovingly”) (John 1:3; Hebrews 12). But the “Good News”^[6] is that without sin, humankind would not have Jesus Christ its Saviour, given to them by God (as accounted for by the Gospels). This is the news of salvation, or liberation from the disconnection and

estrangement from God that sin causes.^[7] Jesus Christ gives the world hope again by dying on the Cross for humankind's sins, and the "many will be made righteous." (Romans 5:18–19)

Hamartiology is the study of the Biblical concept of sin. There are many salient words in the Bible that represent sin and theologians have argued for thousands of years over what the entire Doctrine of Sin comprises. Chata (Greek: Hamartano) occurs about 522 times in the Old Testament, and its basic meaning is to "miss the mark."^[8] But this is not to mean that it is something passive in nature, because by missing the mark, one hits some other mark.^[9] Harmatano can be said to occur in "moral evil, idolatry, and ceremonial sins. Some important references include Ex 20:20; Jud 20:16; Prov 8:36; 19:2."^[10] Ra is used over 400 times in the Old Testament, and this word, equivalent to Kakos or Poneros, basically means the breaking up or ruining of something. In Isaiah 45:7, God is said to create light and darkness, well-being and Ra. Pasha means rebellion, or transgression. Awon, Shagag, Asham, Rasha and Taah mean a variety of sins that have "wickedness" at their core (Exodus 2:13; Psalms 9:16; Proverbs 15:9; Ezekiel 18:23),^[11] and being led astray from God (whilst being deliberate about it) (Numbers 15:22; Psalms 58:3; 119:21; Isaiah 53:6; and Ezekiel 44:10, 15).^[12]

Like Hamartano, Hamartia means missing the mark (and hitting the wrong mark). However, unlike the Old Testament, it is often spoken of in terms of forgiveness or salvation (Matthew 1:21, John 1:29).^[13] It is the main (but not the only) word for sin used in the

New Testament, but it is the most frequently used (over 200 times).^[14] Other words include Kakos, Poneros, Asebes, Enochos, Adikia, Anomos, Parabates, Agnoein, Planao, Parapt-oma, and Hypocrisis.^[15] But what Paul found most problematic in respect of all these forms was the idea of sin as a “power and principle” in connection with “human nature.”^[16]

Collating all these words and concepts through Hamartiology has led to extensive attempts to define sin by theologians. Elmer L. Town noted the difficulty in homing in to one exclusive definition,^[17] for example: “Any thought, word or action that violates God’s rules.”^[18] E. A. Martens defines it as “an action and attitude in opposition to God and His purposes. It is the violation of God’s will and righteousness, disloyalty, disobedience, the breaching of a harmonious and just relationship with God, others, self, and nature.”^[19] This is more apt since it highlights the damaged relationship that the sinner has with God. Seamlessly grappling with the technicality and difficulty of the Doctrine of Sin and presenting it in the contemporary vernacular is the extensive definition provided by Beth Felker Jones:

Sin is multi-layered and dense. It is both individual and corporate, infecting individual human beings and human institutions. Sin is both personal and systemic. While it belongs to humans in a special way, it also injures creation, which groans under its weight (Rom. 8:22). Sin extends to every aspect of human life: into body and soul, our ways of knowing and our emotions, work and

relationships, hopes and desires. Sin separates us from the holiness of God.[\[20\]](#)

The concept of Original Sin is important when considering the entire concept of the Doctrine of Sin. The first human beings (Adam and Eve) were created by God, in His likeness, and He judged that they were “very good” (Genesis 1:31). But the serpent tempted Adam and Eve into sinning (by eating the forbidden fruit) which brought about the fall of humanity (Genesis 3). The serpent represented Lucifer, a fallen angel, demonstrating that sin did in fact exist prior to Genesis (Ezekiel 28:14–15; Isaiah 14:12–15).[\[21\]](#) As the (hereditary) children of Adam, all humans have sin in their nature. Humanity over history need only be honest that it is far from perfect. But each person is also guilty of their deeds. Therefore, all humans are declared to be sinners in the sight of God.[\[22\]](#) And as in the case of the fall of Lucifer,[\[23\]](#) where the relevant sin was pride, Adam and Eve’s sin was also one of pride; by disobeying God and wanting to be “like God, knowing good and evil (Genesis 3:4).”[\[24\]](#) It follows that in examining the origin of sin and its imputation or inheritance, pride is likely to be the root cause of all sin.[\[25\]](#) Proverbs 16:18 says that, “Pride goes before destruction, a haughty spirit before a fall.”

By definition, imputation means that Adam’s sin has been credited to the account of every person who has ever lived or ever will live (Romans 5:12–21).[\[26\]](#) There has been much theological speculation over the Doctrine of Imputation over many centuries; many conflicting. Augustinism is a theory that splits the notion of Original Sin into two: 1. The “historical event of Adam and Eve’s sin” and 2.

“The condition of sin in humankind caused by the transmission of Adam and Eve’s sin to all.”[\[27\]](#) Pelagianism is the most noted theological opponent of the concept of Original Sin.[\[28\]](#) It maintained that infants were born without sin, but this brings the fear that belief in Original Sin would act as a disincentive to a Christian’s attempt to live a moral life.[\[29\]](#) “If human nature has a predisposition toward evil, why try to do the good?”[\[30\]](#) Arminianism/Semi-Pelagianism are theories that consider the notion Adam’s “pollution of sin” being imputed to humanity. Human is by nature a sinner, but humans are not guilty of Adam’s sin. God also gives each person sufficient grace at the time of birth, which counteracts the sinful tendency inherited from Adam and leaves humanity morally neutral.[\[31\]](#) But humanity follows Adam via personal sin (Romans 5:12). “Semi-Pelagianism is a mediating position between Augustinism (with its strong emphasis on predestination and human’s inability) and Pelagianism (with its insistence on human’s complete ability).”[\[32\]](#) The Federal Theory dictates that as Adam was the appointed head of the race, his sin is imputed to humankind. Thus, Romans 5:12 means that all people are responsible for the sin of Adam, their representative, even though they did not personally commit that sin.[\[33\]](#)

Williams hints at a vague notion of Original Sin being that which piques the individual conscience (that is, humankind’s sense of what is right and wrong).[\[34\]](#) It is an atheistic alternative to Scripture that highlights humanity’s inherent depravity. Whether one looks through the various lenses of the imputation or inheritance of Original Sin, or personal sin, a sinner’s intellect is blinded (2 Corinthians 4:4), their minds are reprobate or disapproved (Romans

1:28), their understanding is darkened and separated from the life of God (Ephesians 4:18), their emotions are degraded and defiled (Romans 1:21, 24, 26; Titus 1:15), and their will is enslaved to sin and therefore stand in opposition to God (Romans 6:20; 7:20). The aftermath of the act or omission that comprises the sin can be the most tortuous period for the sinner, as illustrated by the character of Lady Macbeth in Shakespeare's play *Macbeth*:

Naught's had, all's spent,

Where our desire is got without content.

Tis safer to be that which we destroy

Than by destruction dwell in doubtful joy.[\[35\]](#)

The act of sin alone is a travesty, and this is set out in Scripture, but it is not just one event. The pain felt by victims (including God) and perpetrators continues after the event, such as in the case of the character of Lady Macbeth, who could not bear the guilt of committing murder. Sin is “the state of alienation of God.”[\[36\]](#) It ruptures humankind's relationship with God as they look away from Him through their actions, and they must carry their burden — enduring the problem of pain and evil. It is clear, from early Scripture onwards, that there is a theme of alienation connected with sin, as God says to Cain, “You will be a fugitive and a wanderer on the earth” (Genesis 4:12). God also separates Himself from His people in Genesis 12 and Exodus 33:3. He cannot be with the “stiff-

necked people” as He is holy and cannot be with sin. By sinning, humans destroy God’s good work. Humans are meant to be made in His image, but the truth is they are living a lie: “The sinner’s life becomes a sham existence.”^[37] By being unfaithful to God, humankind has “exchanged the truth about God for a lie” (Romans 1:25). And most heartbreaking of all, in Paul’s view, “There is no one who is righteous, not even one.” (Romans 3:10)

Examining the Doctrine of Sin can be depressing and overwhelming, with the burden of the concept of Original Sin, the nature of sin, and the prevalence of personal sin causing so much misery and disconnect in the world. But it is important to make the salient point, that without sin, “the Gospel message loses much of its power and purpose. To fully appreciate the “good news” of the Christ’s redemption, we first must grapple with the “bad news” of our fallen condition.”^[38] Ultimately, God loves humankind so much that He sent His Son Jesus Christ to reconcile their Sins. As the apostle Paul said:

Consequently, just as one trespass resulted in condemnation for all people, so also one righteous act resulted in justification and life for all people. For just as through the disobedience of one man, the many were made sinners, so also through the obedience of the one man, the many will be made righteous. (Romans 5:18–19)

The New Testament contains this Good News which is revealed through Jesus’ ministry, death and resurrection.^[39] “Our Sin was put on Jesus so that His righteousness would be counted to

us.”^[40] Despite many arguments between many theologians over centuries, it is safe to assume that the accepted position of the Good News is that no sin cannot be forgiven, if the sinner truly repents and remains devoted to God (although nuances exist between the Christian churches on this point).^[41] But none of these nuances can deviate from the actual words of the Gospels, which are at the cornerstone of the faith and devotion of humankind to Jesus Christ, the Messiah: “Behold, the Lamb of God, who takes away the sin of the world.” (John 1:29) This Good News brings to fullness the Doctrine of Sin in a way that allows humankind to move forward with redemption; without forever being burdened by Adam’s sin within them, or by any other personal sin committed by them, if they wholly repent and turn to God, thereby remaining connected with Him.

End Notes:

^[1] Roy Williams, *God Actually* (Sydney: ABC Books, 2008), 81–82.

^[2] Williams, *God Actually*, 81–82.

^[3] Charles Darwin, *On the Origin of the Species by Means of Natural Selection, or Preservation of Favoured Races in the Struggle for Life* (London: John Murray, 1859). Richard Dawkins, *The God Delusion* (London: Bantam Press, 2006).

^[4] Charles Darwin, *On the Origin of the Species*; Dawkins, *The God Delusion*

[5] Williams, *God Actually*, 81–82.

[6] Bobby Jamieson, “What is the Good News,” *Explore God*, Accessed April 20, 2022, <https://www.exploregod.com/articles/what-is-the-good-news>.

[7] C. Clifton Black, “The “Good News” of the New Testament,” *Bible Odyssey: Ask a Scholar*, Accessed April 20, 2022, <https://www.bibleodyssey.org/ea/tools/ask-a-scholar/good-news-of-the-nt>.

[8] Charles C. Ryrie, *Basic Theology: A Popular Systematic Guide to Understanding Biblical Truth* (Grand Rapids: Zondervan Publishing House, 1999), 447.

[9] Ryrie, *Basic Theology*, 447; Harold Willmington, “The Doctrine of Sin,” *The Forbidden Fruit File*, Accessed April 20, 2022, http://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/forbidden_fruit/1/, 2.

[10] Ryrie, *Basic Theology*, 447; Willmington, “The Doctrine of Sin,” 2.

[11] Ryrie, *Basic Theology*, 448; Paul R. House, “Sin in the Former and Latter Prophets and the Writings,” in *Fallen: A Theology of Sin*, eds Christopher W. Morgan and Robert A. Peterson (Pennsylvania: WTS Books, 2013), Chapter 2.

[12] Ryrie, *Basic Theology*, 448; House, “Sin in the Former and Latter Prophets and the Writings,” Chapter 2.

[13] Ryrie, *Basic Theology*, 449; Robert W. Yarbrough, “Sin in the Gospels, Acts and Hebrews to Revelation,” in *Fallen: A Theology of Sin*, eds Christopher W. Morgan and Robert A. Peterson (Pennsylvania: WTS Books, 2013), Chapter 4.

[14] Ryrie, *Basic Theology*, 449; Yarbrough, “Sin in the Gospels,” Chapter 4.

[15] Ryrie, *Basic Theology*, 450; Yarbrough, “Sin in the Gospels,” Chapter 4.

[16] Orello Cone, “The Pauline Doctrine of Sin,” *The American Journal of Theology* II, no.2 (1898): 242; Douglas J. Moo, “Sin in the Gospels, Acts and Hebrews to Revelation,” in *Fallen: A Theology of Sin*, eds Christopher W. Morgan and Robert A. Peterson (Pennsylvania: WTS Books, 2013), Chapter 5.

[17] Elmer L. Town, *Theology for Today* (Belmont: Wadsworth/Thomson Learning, 2002), 500.

[18] Anderson A. Gray, *Sin: A History* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2009), 10.

[19] E. A. Martens, “Sin Guilt,” in *Dictionary of the Old Testament: Pentateuch*, ed T. Desmond Alexander and David W. Baker (Downers Grove: InterVarsity Press, 2003), 764

[20] Beth Felker Jones, *Practicing Christian Doctrine: An Introduction to Thinking and Living Theologically* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2014), 108–109.

[21] Derek R. Nelson, *Sin: A Guide for the Perplexed* (London: T&T Clark, 2011), 51; Don Stewart, “How do we understand the Serpent in the Garden of Eden?” *Blue Letter Bible*, Accessed on 20 April, 2022, https://www.blueletterbible.org/faq/don-stewart/don_stewart_705.cfm.

[22] Millard J. Erickson, *Christian Theology (3rd ed)* (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2015), 391.

[23] Erickson, *Christian Theology*, 535.

[24] Felker Jones, *Practicing Christian Doctrine*, 108.

[25] Ian McFarland, *Adam’s Fall: A Mediation on the Christian Doctrine of Original Sin* (Chichester: Wiley Blackwell, 2010), 19.

[26] *The Vocabulary of the Greek Testament* (London: Hodder and Stoughton, 1914), 377.

[27] Moulton and Milligan, *The Vocabulary of the Greek Testament*, 349–350; Ernesto Bonaiuti and Giorgio La Piana, “The Genesis of St. Augustine’s Idea of Original Sin,” *Harvard Theological Review* 10, no. 2 (1917): 175.

[28] Tatha Wiley, *Original Sin: Origins, Developments, Contemporary Meanings* (New York: Paulist Press, 2002), 7.

[29] Piet Fransen, *Augustine, Pelagius and the Controversy on the Doctrine of Grace* (Louvain: University of Louvain — Faculty of Theology, 1987), 172–181;

[30] Wiley, *Original Sin*, 7.

[31] Ryrie, *Basic Theology*, 459.

[32] *Ibid.*, 459.

[33] *Ibid.*, 459.

[34] Williams, *God Actually*, 81–82.

[35] William Shakespeare, *Macbeth* (Ware: Wordsworth Classics, 1992), Act 3 Scene 2

[36] Donald G. Bloesch, “Definition of Sin,” in *Evangelical Dictionary of Theology*, ed. Walter A. Elwell (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1984), 1012.

[37] Eberhard Jungel, *Justification: The Heart of the Christian Faith* (London: T&T Clark, 2001), 110; Felker Jones, *Practicing Christian Doctrine*, 110.

[38] Andre Villeneuve, “The Bad News and the Good News: Original Sin and the Gospel Message,” *Catechetics*, Accessed on 22 April, 2022, <https://review.catechetics.com/bad-news-and-good-news-original-sin-and-gospel-message/>.

[39] Black, “The “Good News” of the New Testament.”

[40] Jamieson, “What is the Good News.”

[41] Alister McGrath, *The Christian Theology Reader (5th ed)* (Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 2017), 399–401; Beth Haile, “Can Everyone Be Forgiven?” *USA Catholic*, Accessed on 22 April, 2022, <https://usacatholic.com/articles/201708/can-every-sin-be-forgiven/>.

Bibliography:

Black, Clifton C. “The “Good News” of the New Testament.” *Bible Odyssey: Ask a Scholar*. Accessed April 20, 2022, <https://www.bibleodyssey.org/ea/tools/ask-a-scholar/good-news-of-the-nt/>.

Bloesch, Donald G. “Sin.” In *Evangelical Dictionary of Theology*, definition on page 1012. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 1984.

Bonaiuti, Ernesto and Li Piana, Giorgio. "The Genesis of St. Augustine's Idea of Original Sin." *Harvard Theological Review* 10, no. 2 (1917): 159–175.

Cone, Orello, "The Pauline Doctrine of Sin," *The American Journal of Theology* II, no. 2 (1898): 241–267.

Darwin, Charles. *On the Origin of the Species by Means of Natural Selection, or Preservation of Favoured Races in the Struggle for Life*. London: John Murray, 1859.

Dawkins, Richard. *The God Delusion*. London: Bantam Press, 2006.

Erickson, Millard J. *Christian Theology (3rd ed)*. Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2015.

Felker Jones, Beth. *Practicing Christian Doctrine: An Introduction to Thinking and Living Theologically*. Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2014.

Fransen, Piet. *Augustine, Pelagius and the Controversy on the Doctrine of Grace*. Louvain: University of Louvain — Faculty of Theology, 1987.

Gray, Anderson A. *Sin: A History*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2009.

Haile, Beth. "Can Everyone Be Forgiven?" *USA Catholic*. Accessed on 22 April, 2022. <https://usacatholic.com/articles/201708/can-every-sin-be-forgiven/>.

House, Paul R. "Sin in the Former and Latter Prophets and the Writings." In *Fallen: A Theology of Sin*, edited by Christopher W. Morgan and Robert A. Peterson, Chapter 2. Pennsylvania: WTS Books, 2013.

Jamieson, Bobby. "What is the Good News." *Explore God*. Accessed April 20, 2022. <https://www.exploregod.com/articles/what-is-the-good-news/>.

Jungel, Eberhard. *Justification: The Heart of the Christian Faith*. London: T&T Clark, 2001.

Martens, E. A. "Sin Guilt." In *Dictionary of the Old Testament: Pentateuch*, edited by T. Desmond Alexander and David W. Baker, definition on page 764. Downers Grove: InterVarsity Press, 2003).

McFarland, Ian. *Adam's Fall: A Mediation on the Christian Doctrine of Original Sin*. Chichester: Wiley Blackwell, 2010.

McGrath, Alister. *The Christian Theology Reader (5th ed)*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, 2017.

Moo, Douglas J. "Sin in the Gospels, Acts and Hebrews to Revelation." In *Fallen: A Theology of Sin*, edited by Christopher W.

Morgan and Robert A. Peterson, Chapter 5. Pennsylvania: WTS Books, 2013.

Morgan, Christopher W. and Peterson, Robert A. *Fallen: A Theology of Sin*. Pennsylvania: WTS Books, 2013.

Moulton and Milligan. *The Vocabulary of the Greek Testament*. London: Hodder and Stoughton, 1914.

Nelson, R. *Sin: A Guide for the Perplexed*. London: T&T Clark, 2011.

Ryrie, Charles C. *Basic Theology: A Popular Systematic Guide to Understanding Biblical Truth*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan Publishing House, 1999.

Shakespeare, William. *Macbeth*. Ware: Wordsworth Classics, 1992.

Stewart, Don. "How do we understand the Serpent in the Garden of Eden?" *Blue Letter Bible*. Accessed on 20 April 2022. https://www.blueletterbible.org/faq/don-stewart/don_stewart_705.cfm.

Town, Elmer L. *Theology for Today*. Belmont: Wadsworth/Thomson Learning, 2002.

Villeneuve, Andre. "The Bad News and the Good News: Original Sin and the Gospel Message." *Catechetics*. Accessed on 22 April,

2022. <https://review.catechetics.com/bad-news-and-good-news-original-sin-and-gospel-message/>.

Wiley, Tatha. *Original Sin: Origins, Developments, Contemporary Meanings*. New York: Paulist Press, 2002.

Williams, Roy. *God Actually*. Sydney: ABC Books, 2008.

Willmington, Harold. "The Doctrine of Sin." *The Forbidden Fruit File*. Accessed April 20, 2022. http://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/forbidden_fruit/1/, 2.

Yarbrough, Robert W. "Sin in the Gospels, Acts and Hebrews to Revelation." In *Fallen: A Theology of Sin*, edited by Christopher W. Morgan and Robert A. Peterson, Chapter 4. Pennsylvania: WTS Books, 2013.